

Core Web Vitals Assessment of Pakistani Government Websites: A Comprehensive Analysis

Abstract

This study evaluates the Core Web Vitals (CWV) performance of various Pakistani government websites using Google's PageSpeed Insights tool. Metrics such as Largest Contentful Paint (LCP), First Input Delay (FID), and Cumulative Layout Shift (CLS) provide critical insights into user experience on digital platforms. Among other websites, the study looks at those run by the Higher Education Commission (HEC), the National Database and Registration Authority (NADRA), and the Federal Board of Revenue (FBR). The report highlights important performance problems and provides doable suggestions for improving the provision of public services. The results highlight how urgently changes must be made to satisfy Google's requirements and provide smooth access to crucial digital services.

Introduction

For the delivery of governmental services, information access, and citizen involvement, government websites are essential. Usability and trust are ensured by optimal performance. On the other hand, access to vital services is hampered by pages that load slowly, lack interaction, and have erratic layouts.

Three important performance parameters can be assessed using a standardised framework provided by Google's Core Web Vitals (CWV) initiative:

1. **Largest Contentful Paint (LCP):** The largest visible content's rendering speed is measured by the Largest Contentful Paint (LCP).
2. **First Input Delay (FID):** The responsiveness of user interactions is assessed by the First Input Delay (FID).
3. **Cumulative Layout Shift (CLS):** When a page loads, Cumulative Layout Shift (CLS) evaluates the visual stability.

This study assesses the CWV performance of well-known Pakistani government websites, finds reoccurring problems, and offers optimisation techniques to improve their accessibility and usability.

Core Web Vitals Overview

Core Web Vitals focuses on three user-centric metrics essential for a smooth web experience:

Table 1 summarizes the ideal thresholds for these metrics:

Metric	Description	Ideal Threshold
LCP	Loading speed for largest visible content	≤ 2.5 seconds
FID	Responsiveness to first user interaction	< 100 ms
CLS	Visual stability during loading	< 0.1

These thresholds are benchmarks for evaluating website performance on both mobile and desktop platforms.

Methodology

The CWV of a few chosen Pakistani government websites was examined using Google's PageSpeed Insights service. Both desktop and mobile versions were evaluated, and the findings were categorised as "Passed" or "Failed" according to CWV standards.

- **Website Selection:** The Citizen Portal, FBR, NADRA, HEC, DGIP, PMHealth, PMDC, and PLRA are among the websites that were examined.
- **Metrics Evaluated:** For every website version, the following metrics were assessed: LCP, FID, and CLS.
- **Limitations:** Third-party integrations, server settings, and backend optimisations were outside the purview of the research.

Results and Analysis

Core Web Vitals Assessment Table

Website	Mobile Performance	Desktop Performance	Result
Federal Board of Revenue (FBR)	FBR Mobile	FBR Desktop	Failed (Both)
National Database and Registration Authority (NADRA)	NADRA Mobile	NADRA Desktop	Failed (Both)
Higher Education Commission (HEC)	HEC Mobile	HEC Desktop	Failed (Both)
Director General Immigration and Passports (DGIP)	DGIP Mobile	DGIP Desktop	Passed (Mobile), Failed (Desktop)
PMHealth Program	PMHealth Mobile	PMHealth Desktop	Failed (Both)
Pakistan Medical and Dental Council (PMDC)	PMDC Mobile	PMDC Desktop	Failed (Both)
Punjab Land Record Authority (PLRA)	PLRA Mobile	PLRA Desktop	Failed (Both)
Citizen Portal	Citizen Portal	-	SSL Certificate Verification Failed

Discussion

The majority of websites have systematic performance problems, according to the research.

Among the main obstacles are:

- **Slow Loading Times (LCP):** Rendering is considerably delayed by poorly optimised graphics and complex code.
- **Poor Interactivity (FID):** Outdated frameworks and third-party scripts make it difficult to respond.
- **Visual Instability (CLS):** User experience is disrupted by layout changes brought on by dynamically loaded material.

Recommendations

1. **Adopt Content Delivery Networks (CDNs):** By using servers that are closer to you geographically, you can lower latency.
2. **Implement Lazy Loading:** Use lazy loading to only load non-essential resources, such as pictures, when needed.
3. **Conduct Regular Audits:** Check websites against CWV standards on a regular basis and make necessary corrections.
4. **Enhance Security Protocols:** Resolve SSL certificate problems as soon as possible to keep accessibility.
5. **Modernize Web Practices:** Educate development teams on contemporary optimisation methods, such as following CWV standards.

Conclusion

The Core Web Vitals evaluation of Pakistani government websites reveals serious issues with stability, interaction, and performance. Improving public trust and guaranteeing seamless access to digital services require addressing these problems. These websites may offer quicker, more dependable, and easier-to-use experiences by implementing the suggested guidelines, enhancing their function in digital governance.

Future Work

For practical insights, more research might examine backend optimisations, assess user input about usability, and compare Pakistani government websites to others across the world.

References

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